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Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjabana: Analysis of Literary Criticism

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Abstract

Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, an Indonesian literary figure, captivates audiences not only with his beautiful language but also with the deep messages embedded in his pantun, a form of traditional Malay poetry. Pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana displays themes related to the past and present. In this analysis, we will focus on the dynamics of the structure and meaning contained in Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's pantun. This analysis employs a literary criticism approach to understand the meaning of the pantun. Using critical literary analysis, this article aims to reveal the dynamic interaction between structure and meaning in Alisjahbana pantun, highlighting its artistry and the potential of pantun as a medium for conveying deep messages.

Keyword: Pantun; Literary Critical Analysis; Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana

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INTRODUCTION

Research Problem

The research "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana: Analysis of Literary Criticism" focuses on several important aspects, namely: the physical and mental structure of pantun, the meaning and value of pantun, as well as literary criticism of Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's pantun. The theoretical framework used by researchers for research on "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's Pantun: Literary Critical Analysis" is structuralism, semiotics, and critical theory.

Importance of Research for Field

Study Researchers can directly observe and understand the interpretation and use of STA pantuns in society through this field. This can help researchers find hidden meanings in STA patterns that may not be revealed through text analysis alone. Researchers can observe the use of STA rhymes in diverse social and cultural contexts, including traditional events, religious rituals, and daily life.

Research or Theoretical Gap

This research has the potential to produce significant findings. However, there could be several theoretical gaps in this research that require attention. There are several possible theoretical gaps, such as the lack of a comprehensive theoretical framework, insufficient data, and unclear research boundaries.

Novelty of Research

The research entitled "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana: Analysis of Literary Criticism" has a significant aspect of novelty. The novelty of the research is in terms of analysis, data sources, and theoretical implications.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the structural features of pantun, a traditional Malay poetic form, as found in the works of Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, a prominent Indonesian writer and literary critic.
2. To analyze the meaning and message conveyed through this poem, consider Alisjahbana's own critical perspective on literature and society.
3. We are conducting a literary analysis of the pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana.

Role of Researchers

The researcher's role in the research "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's Pantun: Literary Critical Analysis" is diverse and includes various responsibilities during the research process in terms of data collection and analysis, reviewing literature or in-depth theoretical foundations, and conceptualizing the research topic.

METHOD

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-qualitative method in which the researcher listened to a collection of pantuns by Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana (STA) and noted important points according to the problem that had been formulated by the researcher.

Data Sources

The data obtained came from previous research, and the author updated it to make it more complex.

Data Collection and Procedure

We collected data comprehensively and accurately using literature study methods, literary critical analysis, and analysis of the meaning of pantun. Researchers can adapt research procedures to meet their specific needs and objectives.

Data Analysis

Research on "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's Pantun: Literary Critical Analysis" uses a combination of qualitative techniques to analyze the structure and meaning of pantun, a traditional Malay poem consisting of four lines. The specific techniques used will depend on the research question and theoretical framework of the study.

Some of the qualitative techniques used are close reading, which involves re-reading the rhymes carefully to identify patterns, themes, and meanings.

Accuracy and Trustworthiness

Steps to maintain data accuracy in research on "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in the Pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisjabana (STA)" are selecting the right data source, using accurate data techniques, and triangulating data to strengthen research findings. To increase the trustworthiness of the research "Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Sutan Takdir Alisjabana's Pantun: Literary Critical Analysis," the following steps can be taken: strengthening educational methodology, enriching research data, improving argumentation and discussion, and clarifying what the research contributions are.

Ethical Review

The collected data has undergone a licensing process, agreement, approval, or compliance with regulations.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

You must Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, a giant of Indonesian literature, left an indelible mark on the nation's cultural landscape. His contributions not only include monumental works such as *Layar Terkembang* and *Lentera* but also include a variety of literary works, including his profound and captivating pantun. The definition of pantun as a literary work consisting of four lines and rhyming abab is, of course, important for physically identifying pantun, but it is not enough to raise awareness that pantun is the result of the community's oral traditions, which contain noble values.

These traditional Malay poetry forms, with their concise structures and complex wordplay, provide a platform for Alisjahbana to convey a multitude of messages, including moral, social, and nationalistic themes. Exploring the dynamic interaction between structure and meaning in Alisjahbana pantun requires a critical literary analysis approach. This framework provides a lens through which to examine the complex relationship between form and content in his works, revealing the layers of meaning embedded in his carefully crafted structures. Adherence to the four-line structure of pantun, with its internal rhyme and rhythm, creates a sense of order and harmony, providing a foundation for Alisjahbana to build his messages. Careful selection of words, phrases, and images in each line shapes the thematic and semantic content of the pantun, adding depth and nuance to the message conveyed.

Example of a pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisyahbana:

Pigeons on teak branches
Flying around looking for food
My heart misses me immensely
Want to meet your eternal idol.

Analysis of pantun by Sutan Takdir Alisyahbana

Rhyme structure

The rhyme above consists of four lines with an ABBA rhyme pattern. The sampiran is the first stanza, and the content is the second. This pantun sampiran uses a figure of speech to compare the subject (heart) with the object (dove). This rhyme's content expresses feelings of deep longing for the person you love.

Meaning of Pantun

This pantun uses several figures of speech to strengthen the meaning, such as:

- **Simile figure of speech:** "A dove on a teak branch" is likened to a "heart" that "flies around looking for food".
- **Hyperbolic figure of speech:** "My heart misses me immensely" shows a very deep feeling of longing.
- **Metaphor:** "I want to meet my eternal idol" shows that the poet really loves and appreciates his idol.

This rhyme expresses feelings of deep longing for someone you love. The poet uses various figures of speech to strengthen the meaning of the rhyme and make it more interesting to read.

Literary Critical Analysis

Based on literary critical analysis, this pantun can be analyzed from various points of view, such as:

- **Structural point of view:** This pantun has a neat and orderly structure, with an ABBA rhyme pattern. The ending and content of the poem are related to each other.
- **Semiotic point of view:** This pantun uses various symbols to convey meaning, such as "dove" which symbolizes "heart", "teak branch" which symbolizes "life", and "eternal worship" which symbolizes "true love".
- **Sociocultural perspective:** This pantun reflects the cultural values of Indonesian society, such as love and respect for parents.

Apart from that, the analysis of pantun is based on literary critical analysis studies:

1. Alisjahbana's mastery of the pantun form can be seen from the harmonious combination of structure and meaning.
2. The use of natural similes such as "doves" and "teak branches" grounds these metaphors in the real world, making them relevant.
3. The parallelism between the birds' search for food and the speaker's search for love highlights the intensity of their longing.

Research Significance

Research on the Dynamics of Structure and Meaning in Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's Pantun: Literary Critical Analysis has the potential to positively impact society in several ways.

1. Increase public understanding of Pantun

This research can help people understand pantun more deeply, both in terms of structure and meaning. Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, a renowned Indonesian writer, can analyze various pantuns to achieve this.

2. Encouraging Appreciation of Indonesian Literary Works

This research can also encourage people to better appreciate Indonesian literary works, especially pantun. We can achieve this by introducing pantun to the wider community through mass media and formal and non-formal education.

CONCLUSION

Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, a giant of Indonesian literature, left an indelible mark on the nation's cultural landscape. The rhyme above consists of four lines with an ABBA rhyme pattern. The sampiran is the first stanza, and the content is the second. This pantun sampiran uses a figure of speech to compare the subject (heart) with the object (dove). This rhyme's content expresses feelings of deep longing for the person you love. This rhyme expresses feelings of deep longing for someone you love. The poet uses various figures of speech to strengthen the meaning of the rhyme and make it more enjoyable to read.

Recommendation for Future Research

We hope to carry out this research in the future by comparing the structure and meaning of Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's pantuns with those of other poets. This can help to understand the uniqueness and characteristics of Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana's pantun.

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DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

In this article, there were no potential conflicts of interest with respect to research, authorship, and/or publication.

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